

REACTIVE THERMOPLASTIC RESIN AS A MATRIX FOR LAMINATES CONTAINING MICROENCAPSULATED PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS

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Keywords: Thermal energy storage; Reactive thermoplastic resin; Phase change materials; Multifunctional composites; Dynamic-mechanical analysis.

ABSTRACT

This work aims at developing thermoplastic laminates combining structural and heat management functions. The laminates are composed of continuous carbon fibers as the reinforcement, microencapsulated paraffin as the phase change material (PCM), and the newly developed thermoplastic liquid acrylic resin Elium[®], processable as a thermosetting polymer. The characterization aims to study how the paraffin microcapsules influence the thermo-mechanical properties and thermal management performance of the resin and the carbon laminates. For the resin/PCM systems, the phase change enthalpy increases with the experimental PCM concentration up to 101 J/g. The melting enthalpy of the laminates also increases with the microcapsule amount, up to 66.8 J/g, which indicates that the mild conditions applied in the processing of the liquid resin allow the preservation of the integrity of the microcapsules. This is also confirmed by the improved thermal management performance observed through thermal camera imaging. However, the microcapsules are preferentially distributed in the interlaminar zone, which justifies the decrease in the interlaminar strength and the flexural properties. These results show potential for the future development of multifunctional thermoplastic composites with high thermal energy storage capabilities.

1 INTRODUCTION

The term “thermal energy storage” (TES) refers to a collection of techniques and processes that allow the temporary storage of excess thermal energy, which can be subsequently released where and when needed, thereby narrowing the energy demand-supply gap [1]. Among all the classes of materials that can store and release sensible, latent or thermochemical heat, the most widely employed are the organic solid-liquid phase change materials (PCMs), such as paraffin waxes, polyethylene glycols (PEG) and fatty acids [2]. They can accumulate a noticeable amount of latent heat in a well-defined temperature interval, exhibit a reduced volume change during phase transition, have low density, a tunable working temperature, and a little supercooling degree [3, 4]. As they melt and crystallize at a nearly constant temperature, they are often the preferred choice in thermal management applications, such as the building industry and as passive cooling media of electronic components [5-7].

On the other hand, the main disadvantages of organic PCMs are the low thermal conductivity and the need to be confined to avoid leakage above the melting temperature. The first issue is normally addressed through conductive metallic or carbon-based fillers [8, 9], while the second is generally tackled by encapsulation in macro/micro/nano containers [10, 11] or by shape-stabilization by means of layered or porous materials, nanofiller networks or polymer matrices [12-14].

Heat storage and management systems are often only an additional component, specifically added to perform exclusively that function. However, this can unacceptably rise weight and/or volume and lead to exceed the increasingly strict limits imposed by the lightweight design. In this sense, it would be advantageous to embed the thermal management function directly in the structural components, by means of multifunctional materials combining good mechanical properties and the ability to store and release heat [15].

Although such composites could be helpful in several applications, such as in the automotive and portable electronics fields, they have not been largely investigated so far. Our group produced an epoxy/carbon fiber (CF) composites with paraffin shape-stabilized with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [16,

17] and a glass fiber/polyamide laminate with paraffin microcapsules (MC) [18, 19], thermoplastic and thermosetting composites containing paraffin microcapsules and discontinuous carbon fibers [20, 21], and fully degradable laminates constituted by thermoplastic starch and thin beech laminae impregnated with PEG [22]. These works highlighted that, although thermoplastic composites show well known advantages, the PCM microcapsules hardly withstand the production process in a polymer melt, which leads to capsule break and paraffin leakage.

The aim of this work is to prepare a multifunctional thermoplastic laminate by embedding paraffin microcapsules in the newly developed reactive acrylic resin Elium[®], and to investigate not only the TES capability of the prepared laminates, but also the effects of the MC on the thermo-mechanical properties of the resin and the Elium[®]/CF laminates.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Materials

The employed matrix is Elium[®] 150, kindly provided by Arkema (Colombes, France). It is a liquid, thermoplastic, methyl-methacrylate-based resin, with a viscosity of at room temperature 100 mPa·s. Benzoyl peroxide (BPO) with 50% active content was provided by the same company as a polymerization initiator. The PCM system was the microcapsules (MC) Microtek MPCM43D, supplied by Microtek Laboratories Inc. (Dayton, OH, US), in which the PCM phase is a paraffin wax with a melting temperature of 43 °C, and the shell (approx. 10-15 wt%) is constituted by a melamine-formaldehyde resin. The microcapsules have an average diameter of 17–20 µm and a declared melting enthalpy of 190–200 J/g. The reinforcement phase is constituted by the bi-directional carbon fiber fabric GG200P, purchased from G. Angeloni Srl. (Venice, Italy), having a mass per unit area of 192 g/m².

2.2 Sample preparation

Elium[®] resin and BPO were mixed in a weight ratio of 98:2. The paraffin microcapsules were then added to the matrix in weight concentrations of 20, 30, and 40 wt%, and mechanically stirred at 200 rpm for 5 min. The mixtures were degassed by means of a vacuum pump and poured in rectangular silicon molds of 70×10×3 mm³. The specimens were left at room temperature for four hours and then thermally treated for 8 hours at 80 °C, to complete the polymerization process. The resin/MC systems were labelled EL-MC_x, where x indicates the nominal weight fraction of MC and assumes values of 20, 30 and 40. Specimens of neat resin were prepared for comparison and labelled EL.

The same four compositions were also employed as matrices to prepare laminates via a hand lay-up method. Five plies of carbon fabric were stacked together, and the resulting laminates had an in-plane area of 13×20 cm². The laminates were vacuum-bagged for 4 h at room temperature and thermally treated at 80 °C for 8 h. A neat Elium[®]/CF laminate was also prepared for comparison.

2.3 Characterization

2.3.1 Characterization of the matrices

The microstructural properties of the prepared matrices were investigated through scanning electron microscopy (SEM), performed on cryofractured surfaces with a field-emission SEM Zeiss Supra 60, after Pt-Pd sputtering. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests were performed with a Mettler DSC30 calorimeter, in the temperature interval 0-130 °C, at a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C/min, under a N₂ flow of 100 ml/min. A heating/cooling/heating test was performed on each specimen. The test allowed the measurement of the melting and crystallization temperatures (T_m , T_c) and enthalpy values (ΔH_m , ΔH_c) of the PCM, and the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the resin. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed with a Mettler TG50 instrument on specimens of approximately 25 mg, at a heating rate of 10 °C/min up to 700 °C, in N₂ atmosphere. The tests allowed the determination of the temperatures corresponding to a mass loss of 1 wt% ($T_{1\%}$), 3 wt% ($T_{3\%}$), and 5 wt% ($T_{5\%}$), the peak temperature of the mass loss derivative signal (T_d), and the residual mass (m_r). Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out with a TA Q800DMA instrument in single cantilever bending mode (distance between the grips = 17.5 mm), on specimens with nominal dimensions of 35×10×3 mm³.

Storage modulus (E') and loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) were measured in the temperature interval 0-180 °C at a heating rate of 3 °C/min, with a strain amplitude of 0.05% and a frequency of 1 Hz. Multifrequency scans were carried out at 0.3 mm/min at the frequency values of 0.3, 1, 3, 10 and 30 Hz. The activation energy of the glass transition (E_a) was determined through the Arrhenius equation, from the slope of the linear regression of the natural logarithm of the applied frequency plotted versus the reverse of the $\tan\delta$ peak temperatures. Three-point bending tests were carried out following the standard ASTM D790-03, with an Instron 5969 universal testing machine, equipped with a 50 kN load cell. The nominal dimensions of the tested specimens were 70×10×3 mm³. The tests were performed with a span length of 50 mm and a crosshead speed of 1.5 mm/min. The test allowed the calculation of the tangent modulus of elasticity (E), and the flexural strength (σ_{IM}) and strain at break (ϵ_b).

2.3.2 Characterization of the laminates

The mass fraction of the fibers for each laminate was calculated from the area of the laminate and the mass per unit area of the fabric, and then the matrix (resin + microcapsules) weight fraction for each laminate was calculated by subtracting the mass of the fibers from the total weight of the laminate. The weight composition calculated in this way was compared with that measured through TGA. The experimental density of the laminates was measured with the Archimedes' balance technique in ethanol, through a Gibertini E42 analytical balance. These results allowed the calculation of the volume fraction of the components and the porosity. Optical microscope (OM) images were obtained on the polished cross sections at different magnification levels, through an upright incident-light optical microscope Zeiss Axiophot equipped with Epiplan Neofluar objectives. SEM micrographs of the cryofractured surfaces (cross sections and delamination planes) of all the laminates were acquired through a field-emission SEM Zeiss Supra 60, after Pt-Pd sputtering. DSC and TGA tests were performed in the same experimental conditions used for the matrices. DMA tests were performed as described for the matrices, on samples with nominal in-plane area of 35×5 mm². Moreover, a simple test was performed with a thermal camera to check the overall thermal management capability of the laminates. Rectangular specimens with a surface area of 90×120 mm² were heated in an oven at 60°C for 30 min, then removed and left cooling down to room temperature, while the surface temperature was recorded with the infrared thermal imaging camera FLIR E60. Three-point bending tests were performed with the same equipment used to test the matrices. The tests were performed on specimens with nominal in-plane dimensions of 120×10 mm², with a span length of 85 mm and a crosshead speed of 9 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following section briefly summarizes the results of the characterization of the EL-MC_x samples, and then it focuses on the discussion of the results of the laminates EL-MC_x-CF.

3.1 Characterization of the matrices

Figure 1a and Figure 1b show the SEM micrographs of the cryofracture surface of the samples EL-MC20 and EL-MC40, respectively. The capsules are homogeneously distributed in the polymer matrix, which was also assessed through SEM micrographs acquired at lower magnification. From the broken capsules observable in Figure 1a, the core-shell structure is clearly observable. The shell is smooth and thin, while the core has an irregular morphology. The capsule breakage probably happened during the cryofracture process and not during the sample preparation. The fracture propagation occurs mostly across the capsules and not at the interface, which suggests a rather good capsule-matrix adhesion. However, this is not the case for the sample EL-MC40, in which the fractures propagate at the capsule-matrix interface, probably following the voids and the defects.

The results of the DSC tests are reported in Figure 2. The scan of the neat MC is also reported for comparison. The melting peak is observable for all the samples containing PCM between 40 °C and 60 °C, while the crystallization peak is found on cooling between 40 °C and 20 °C. The melting and crystallization temperatures (Table 1) are respectively higher and lower than those of the MC sample, which implies that the phase change is slightly delayed, likely due to the thermal inertia of the surrounding matrix.

Figure 1: SEM micrographs of the cryofracture surface of the samples EL-MC_x. (a) EL-MC20; (b) EL-MC40

The neat MC exhibits a phase change enthalpy of 208.2 J/g, in good agreement with the value declared by the producer. The phase change enthalpy values of the EL-MC_x samples are slightly higher than those expected by considering the nominal PCM weigh fraction, calculated under the hypothesis that the PCM contained in the MC has the same melting and crystallization properties both free and embedded in the resin. This difference can be explained by taking into account the partial evaporation of the most volatile compounds from the resin during sample preparation, which causes a decrease in the actual resin content and thus an increase in the experimental MC weight fraction. The measurement of the mass loss during processing allowed an estimation of an experimental MC fraction and, in turn, of an expected phase change enthalpy. These values, reported in Table 1, are in good agreement with the experimental enthalpy measured via DSC.

Figure 2: DSC thermograms of the samples EL-MC_x. First heating scan and cooling scan.

Sample	EL (nom. wt%)	MC (nom. wt%)	mass loss (wt%)	MC (exp. wt%)	T _g (°C)	T _m (°C)	ΔH _{m,exp} (J/g)	ΔH _{m,theor} (J/g)	T _c (°C)	ΔH _{c,exp} (J/g)
EL	100.0	-	33.3 ± 3.3	-	103.6	-	-	-	-	-
EL-MC20	80.0	20.0	20.9 ± 1.9	25.3 ± 0.6	103.8	47.0	53.1	52.6 ± 1.3	25.0	53.5
EL-MC30	70.0	30.0	18.6 ± 2.8	36.9 ± 1.2	104.6	47.7	80.8	76.7 ± 2.5	24.8	81.6
EL-MC40	60.0	40.0	16.6 ± 0.7	48.0 ± 0.4	101.7	49.9	101.4	99.8 ± 0.8	23.7	100.1
MC	0	100	-	100	-	45.0	208.2	-	29.8	208.2

Table 1: Nominal and experimental matrix compositions and main results of the DSC tests.

EL = Elium[®] resin + benzoyl peroxide (2 wt%); MC = microcapsules; nom. = nominal; exp. = experimental; T_g = glass transition temperature of the resin; T_m, T_c = melting and crystallization temperatures of the PCM; ΔH_{m,exp}, ΔH_{c,exp} = experimental melting and crystallization enthalpy of the PCM; ΔH_{m,theor} = theoretical melting enthalpy of the PCM calculated from the measured capsule weight fraction MC (exp. wt%).

Table 2 reports the results of the 3-point bending test. It can be observed that the flexural elastic modulus and the flexural strength generally decrease with the MC insertion, which is probably linked to the low mechanical properties of the MC phase. On the other hand, the strain at break is not significantly modified by the introduction of MC.

Sample	E (GPa)	σ _{FM} (MPa)	ε _b (%)
EL	2.08 ± 0.25	63.0 ± 7.3	3.7 ± 0.5
EL-MC20	1.50 ± 0.11	33.2 ± 2.1	3.9 ± 0.4
EL-MC30	1.51 ± 0.10	26.6 ± 2.2	3.4 ± 0.5
EL-MC40	1.35 ± 0.18	17.1 ± 1.8	3.0 ± 0.2

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the samples EL-MCx.

E = flexural elastic modulus; σ_{FM} = flexural strength; ε_b = strain at break.

3.2 Characterization of the laminates

Also the characterization of the laminates involved a microstructural investigation. Representative OM and SEM micrographs of the laminate EL-MC20-CF are reported in Figure 3a and Figure 3b, respectively.

Figure 3: microstructure of the laminate EL-MC20-CF. (a) OM micrograph of the polished cross section; (b) SEM micrograph of the delamination plane.

It can be clearly seen that the PCM concentrates in the interlaminar region, which is due to the relative size of fibers and microcapsules. Moreover, an increase in the initial PCM fraction in the matrix does not cause a substantial increase in the MC density in the interlaminar region. What is seen to increase is the thickness of the interlaminar zone, which in turn determines an increase in the thickness of the whole laminate. This also is at the basis of a decrease in the fiber weight (and volume) fraction with an increase in the MC content, linked to an increase in the total matrix viscosity. This was also confirmed by TGA tests (Figure 4a), which allowed the measurement of the fiber weight fraction (CF_{TGA} wt%) reported in Table 3. and data are in good agreement with the fiber fraction calculated through laminate weighing (CF_{mass} wt%). On the other hand, is difficult to fix *a priori* the final MC weight fraction in the laminate, as it depends on the matrix weight fraction. However, the MC content can be estimated from DSC (Figure 4b), as it is proportional to the the measured phase change enthalpy, provided that the PCM preserves its TES properties also when it is embedded in the laminate.

Figure 4: thermal characterization of the prepared laminates. (a) TGA thermograms; (b) DSC thermograms. First heating scan and cooling scan.

It can be observed that the fiber weight fraction considerably decreases with a rise in the MC loading. The results of this calculation are reported in Table 3. The experimental MC weight fraction ranges from 14.5 wt% for the laminate EL-MC20-CF to 32.3 wt% for the laminate EL-MC40-CF, in which the developed melting enthalpy reaches 66.8 J/g, considerably higher than that obtained on similar laminates so far.

Sample	T_m (°C)	$\Delta H_{m,exp}$ (J/g)	T_c (°C)	$\Delta H_{c,exp}$ (J/g)	MC_{exp} (wt%)	CF_{TGA} (wt%)	CF_{mass} (wt%)	porosity (vol%)	CF (vol%)	MC (vol%)
EL-CF	-	-	-	-	-	65.9	67.8	1.6	56.7	0
EL-MC20-CF	46.6	30.23	27.5	31.6	14.5	48.3	47.8	2.2	35.6	20.95
EL-MC30-CF	45.3	45.9	29.5	45.6	22.1	37.1	40.7	1.2	27.4	30.41
EL-MC40-CF	46.4	66.8	27.4	65.6	32.1	36.9	39.5	5.2	25.0	40.93

Table 3: Main results from the DSC and TGA tests, weight and volume composition of the laminates. T_m , T_c = melting and crystallization temperatures of the PCM; $\Delta H_{m,exp}$, $\Delta H_{c,exp}$ = experimental melting and crystallization enthalpies of the PCM; MC_{exp} = experimental capsule weight fraction calculated from the measured melting enthalpy. CF_{TGA} = fiber weight fraction calculated from TGA residual masses; CF_{mass} = fiber weight fraction calculated from laminate weighing.

This good TES performance was at the basis of the results of the thermal camera imaging test, reported in Figure 5. In the laminates containing the PCM, the temperature decreases with a plateau-like trend, due to the heat released at the paraffin crystallization, this effect, not present in the sample EL-CF, is increasingly evident with an increase in the MC weight fraction, and it is at the basis of the increase in the cooling time.

Figure 5: results of the thermal camera imaging test on the prepared laminates.

Figure 6 reports the main results of the three-point bending test. The elastic modulus and the flexural strength decrease with a rise in the MC content, which is mainly due to the lower fiber fraction. Moreover, the concentration of the MC in the interlaminar region causes a decrease in the interlaminar properties, as delamination can be observed from the load-deflection curves (not reported).

Figure 6: results of the three-point bending test on the prepared laminates.

Finally, also the dynamic-mechanical properties of the laminates are affected by the PCM phase. Figure 7 reports the trends of the storage modulus E' (normalized to the value at 0 °C) and the loss modulus E'' acquired as a function of temperature in the monofrequency tests. For the laminate without MC, the storage modulus exhibits a sharp decrease only at the glass transition, while for the other laminates another step is observable at the melting temperature of the PCM. The amplitude of this step shows a linear correlation ($R^2 > 0.98$) with the MC weight fraction and melting enthalpy, and so does the area under the $\tan\delta$ peak (not reported). However, this step is almost completely recovered on cooling, as demonstrated by cyclic heating-cooling DMA tests.

Multifrequency scans were also performed to investigate the effect of the applied frequency on the signals of the PCM phase change and the glass transition of the resin. An exemplificative thermogram of the sample EL-MC30-CF is reported in Figure 8. As expected the E'' and $\tan\delta$ peaks at the glass transition of the resin shift to higher temperatures with increasing frequency, but it is interesting to observe that also the signal at the PCM melting is affected by the applied frequency, and the frequency sensitivity is higher before than after the maximum. This can be related to the fact that a strong frequency dependence could be found until the first steps of the melting phase change, but when the PCM is almost completely molten the frequency dependence is considerably reduced. The results of the dynamic-mechanical characterization give an interesting insight on the use of DMA techniques to study melting phenomena.

Figure 7: Results of the DMA test on the prepared laminates. Storage modulus (E') and loss modulus (E'') as a function of temperature.

Figure 8: Results of the DMA test on the laminate EL-MC30-CF. Investigated frequencies: 0.3-1-3-10-30 Hz. Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) as a function of temperature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The reactive thermoplastic matrix Elium[®] 150 proved itself suitable for the production of continuous carbon fiber laminates containing phase change microcapsules. The first part of the work was devoted to the characterization of resin/PCM systems, for which DSC tests evidenced the good heat storage/release capability, as the measured phase change enthalpies were proportional to the experimental PCM content (i.e., up to 101 J/g for the sample EL-MC40). This indicates that the mild processing conditions of this resin allowed the microcapsules to retain their TES properties. The characterized resin/PCM compositions were employed as matrices to produce multifunctional thermoplastic laminates with heat storage/management function. The measured phase change enthalpy increased with the MC content, up to 66.8 J/g, which was the reason for the good thermal management performance, measured through thermal camera imaging. OM and SEM analysis showed that the PCM phase was preferentially distributed in the interlaminar zone, and that the laminate thickness and the matrix (Elium[®]+PCM) volume fraction increased with an increase in the capsule content. This brought to a reduction in the mechanical properties of the laminates at high PCM contents, which implies the non-synergistic behavior of the mechanical and TES properties and the need to find a compromise in the composition in line with the specific application. The in-depth DMA analysis gave important information on how the dynamic-mechanical properties of polymer composites are affected by a PCM phase change, which is fundamental for composites designed to combine the structural and TES functions. It also experimented the uncommon use of DMA to study a melting/crystallization phase change and found noteworthy correlations between DMA and DSC parameters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Dr. Pierre Gerard (Arkema, Colombes, France) is gratefully acknowledged for kindly providing the Elium[®] resin.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. S. Fleischer, *Thermal Energy Storage Using Phase Change Materials - Fundamentals and Applications*. Minneapolis, MN, USA: Springer Briefs in Applied Science and Technology. Thermal Engineering and Applied Science. , 2015.
- [2] K. Pielichowska and K. Pielichowski, "Phase change materials for thermal energy storage", *Progress in materials science*, vol. 65, pp. 67-123, 2014.10.1016/j.pmatsci.2014.03.005
- [3] E. M. Anghel, A. Georgiev, S. Petrescu, R. Popov, and M. Constantinescu, "Thermo-physical characterization of some paraffins used as phase change materials for thermal energy storage", *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, vol. 117, pp. 557-566, 2014.10.1007/s10973-014-3775-6
- [4] K. Iqbal, A. Khan, D. Sun, M. Ashraf, A. Rehman, F. Safdar, *et al.*, "Phase change materials, their synthesis and application in textiles—a review", *The Journal of The Textile Institute*, pp. 1-14, 2019.10.1080/00405000.2018.1548088
- [5] L. Bayés-García, L. Ventolà, R. Cordobilla, R. Benages, T. Calvet, and M. A. Cuevas-Diarte, "Phase Change Materials (PCM) microcapsules with different shell compositions: Preparation, characterization and thermal stability", *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 94, pp. 1235-1240, 2010.10.1016/j.solmat.2010.03.014
- [6] A. Lazrak, J.-F. Fourmigué, and J.-F. Robin, "An innovative practical battery thermal management system based on phase change materials: Numerical and experimental investigations", *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 128, pp. 20-32, 2018.10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.08.172

- [7] R. Kandasamy, X.-Q. Wang, and A. S. Mujumdar, "Application of phase change materials in thermal management of electronics", *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 27, pp. 2822-2832, 2007.10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2006.12.013
- [8] Q. Zhang and J. Liu, "Anisotropic thermal conductivity and photodriven phase change composite based on RT100 infiltrated carbon nanotube array", *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 190, pp. 1-5, 2019.10.1016/j.solmat.2018.10.010
- [9] L. Ianniciello, P. H. Biwolé, and P. Achard, "Electric vehicles batteries thermal management systems employing phase change materials", *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 378, pp. 383-403, 2018.10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.12.071
- [10] J.-S. Cho, A. Kwon, and C.-G. Cho, "Microencapsulation of octadecane as a phase-change material by interfacial polymerization in an emulsion system", *Colloid and Polymer Science*, vol. 280, pp. 260-266, 2002.10.1007/s00396-001-0603-x
- [11] P. Felix De Castro and D. G. Shchukin, "New polyurethane/docosane microcapsules as phase-change materials for thermal energy storage", *Chemistry*, vol. 21, pp. 11174-9, Jul 27 2015.10.1002/chem.201500666
- [12] M. Mehrali, S. T. Latibari, M. Mehrali, T. M. I. Mahlia, and H. S. C. Metselaar, "Effect of carbon nanospheres on shape stabilization and thermal behavior of phase change materials for thermal energy storage", *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 88, pp. 206-213, Dec 2014.10.1016/j.enconman.2014.08.014
- [13] Y. Xia, H. Zhang, P. Huang, C. Huang, F. Xu, Y. Zou, *et al.*, "Graphene-oxide-induced lamellar structures used to fabricate novel composite solid-solid phase change materials for thermal energy storage", *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 362, pp. 909-920, 2019.10.1016/j.cej.2019.01.097
- [14] M. M. Umair, Y. Zhang, K. Iqbal, S. Zhang, and B. Tang, "Novel strategies and supporting materials applied to shape-stabilize organic phase change materials for thermal energy storage—A review", *Applied Energy*, vol. 235, pp. 846-873, 2019.10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.11.017
- [15] S. Yoo, E. Kandare, G. Mahendrarajah, M. A. Al-Maadeed, and A. A. Khatibi, "Mechanical and thermal characterisation of multifunctional composites incorporating phase change materials", *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 51, pp. 2631-2642, Aug 2017.10.1177/0021998316673894
- [16] G. Fredi, A. Dorigato, L. Fambri, and A. Pegoretti, "Wax Confinement with Carbon Nanotubes for Phase Changing Epoxy Blends", *Polymers*, vol. 9, p. 405, 2017.10.3390/polym9090405
- [17] G. Fredi, A. Dorigato, L. Fambri, and A. Pegoretti, "Multifunctional epoxy/carbon fiber laminates for thermal energy storage and release", *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 158, pp. 101-111, 2018.10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.02.005
- [18] G. Fredi, A. Dorigato, and A. Pegoretti, "Multifunctional glass fiber/polyamide composites with thermal energy storage/release capability", *EXPRESS polymer letters*, vol. 12, pp. 349-364, 2018.10.3144/expresspolymlett.2018.30
- [19] A. Dorigato, G. Fredi, and A. Pegoretti, "Novel phase change materials using thermoplastic composites", *9th International Conference on "Times of Polymers and Composites". AIP Conference Proceedings.*, vol. 1981, 020044-1–020044-4, 2018.10.1063/1.5045906
- [20] G. Fredi, A. Dorigato, S. Unterberger, N. Artuso, and A. Pegoretti, "Discontinuous carbon fiber/polyamide composites with microencapsulated paraffin for thermal energy storage.", *Journal of applied polymer science*, vol. 136, p. 47408, 2019.10.1002/app.47408
- [21] A. Dorigato, G. Fredi, and A. Pegoretti, "Application of the thermal energy storage concept to novel epoxy/short carbon fiber composites.", *Journal of applied polymer science*, vol. 136, 2019.10.1002/app.47434
- [22] A. Dorigato, G. Fredi, M. Negri, and A. Pegoretti, "Thermo-mechanical behaviour of novel Wood Laminae-Thermoplastic Starch Biodegradable Composites with Thermal Energy Storage/Release capability", *Frontiers in Materials*, vol. 6, pp. 1-12, 2019.10.3389/fmats.2019.00076